

A GOOD CONVERSATION: A PARADIGM SHIFT IN AIRPORT SECURITY

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ABSTRACT

The current article describes a new service design for the security area of Amsterdam Airport Schiphol. In this, a balance has been found between the business needs and the consumer needs. The reported research, including a qualitative study among passengers and diverse stakeholders informed the design process. The corresponding design vision challenged passenger needs, which are ‘personal control’ and ‘guest friendliness’ as well as the needs of the airport business, respectively ‘passenger flow’ and ‘security’. This tension has been addressed by using the metaphor ‘A good conversation’ in the design process, in which the essence of combining business- and consumer needs is grounded. Both the design process and the final design are elaborated upon.

Keywords: Service design, human-centered airport security, paradigm shift.

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide airport security stays high on the political agenda; safety, terrorism and corresponding procedures are under debate when it concerns airport security. Security measures have become stricter and more intensive for passengers in the last few years. Security has become a necessity in which the human perspective has disappeared from sight. At the same time concepts as co-creation, user experience and service design are increasing in importance in designing for business settings. However, within the airport business the current mindset seems to be designing for business needs. Due to the increasing safety regulations for airports, the security checks have become stronger and more intensive for passengers as well. These measures strengthen the feeling of safety on one hand, but on the other hand security is experienced worldwide

more and more as an unpleasant process. When in the following years no (prevented) attacks will take place passengers will not accept this process anymore. Several researches of Amsterdam Airport Schiphol have pointed out that the security process is one of the most important negative influencers of the total quality perception of passengers. Besides, the airport where the research was conducted has a lower score on security in benchmark studies than the most important competing airports. Therefore increasing the quality perception of security has become one of the front lines of the quality policy of Schiphol. The focus to come to an improved quality perception has till now been on a ‘hard side’, emphasizing a higher capacity and a more efficient process. But these process improvements alone turned out to be not enough to improve the quality perception to the level of “Europe’s Preferred Airport”.

For that reason, the current work explores the ‘soft’ side: the surrounding and entourage of the security and the passenger perception. Differently put, the current work aims to develop an innovative concept for the security area that increases the quality perception of the passengers of Schiphol by bringing back the human perspective. This concept has to be able to create a paradigm shift. At the moment changes in the security area are approached in one and the same way. By letting go the current boundaries (a green field approach) the concept can open the eyes of the stakeholders of security by showing a whole new security concept. Figure 1 on the next page outlines the current article and illustrates the structure of the current research and main results for each step (see for details, Hoogervorst, 2010).

Figure 1: Process and main outcomes

CURRENT CONCERNS

Initial research has been conducted to study the current concerns in the airport security context. In a context analysis security was analyzed from different perspectives. The explorative research covered four different researches: a theoretical research into experience and emotions, an expert session on the 'Preferred security experience', a research based on interviews with various stakeholders and personal observations. Main problems identified are the following. Mainly, business passengers are unsatisfied. Elderly are a booming target group. Thus the proposed design should address the needs of these various passenger groups. Next, it appears hard to find qualified security agents. Stress factors among passengers at security need to be reduced. Biometric techniques and self-service are the future. These seem to be opportunities to take into account as well. Moreover, a quick process time is required and passengers need to be better prepared. Last but not least, security has to change from regulation driven to passenger driven.

In parallel, two qualitative passenger studies were executed to find out what makes a security area 'human', based on the opinion of passengers. Their opinion was captured on the main problems at the current security filter, how their ideal security filter would look like and their wishes and dreams. Therefore an experience diary was created to map the current problems followed by a generative session to discover the future wishes and opportunities. It was concluded that passengers prefer in the new security area the following elements: Personal control, clarity, customer

friendly & professional and comfort. The main concerns in the current security were 'overload', lost/stolen luggage, discomfort, no control, be too late, feel rushed and unclear security information.

DESIGN VISION

Awareness for the need of having a passenger focus is rising among the Schiphol organization. Such a passenger focus is required to reach its ambition to be Europe's Preferred Airport. Quality and service are the main issues to attract customers. However to create loyal customers, Schiphol (and the security area) will need to offer something more: They have to exceed the expectations of passengers (Lee, 2004). To realize this in practice, a design vision for future airport security was created enabling Schiphol to exceed these expectations. Personal control and safety form the basis of the new security, the ground. Both have to be present to let the passenger feel human and the security of Schiphol feel in control of the safety. When the ground is created service can be offered: Guest friendliness is added to make passengers feel as a guest, however this cannot reduce the flow of the process. The world around the passenger represents the look & feel of the area: Its main function is decoration. When the person in the landscape would represent an agent, the pressure on the shoulders of the agent becomes obvious: He is responsible for flow, guest friendliness and safety: Three of the four core elements. We envision that future security tasks will change: the agent will be responsible for the safety and guest friendliness and the passenger for the flow and ones personal control.

The look & feel is the responsibility of the airport (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Core elements: the human characteristics.

PERSONAL CONTROL <> SAFETY (HANDING OVER THE CONTROL)

Being 'human' is described in the Van Dale dictionary as "The most gifted creatures on earth". These gifts are that we can think, walk, talk and make things. Control on these aspects is one of our fundamental needs: People fear the things they cannot control and become insecure. Therefore to be in charge is very important for all of us. In the current security area people feel restricted in the way they talk, walk and do things. We feel restricted in our human 'gifts' by needing to hand over the control.

Control in the security area can mainly be given to the passenger on three main fields: offering choices, inform the passenger well and offering the supervision to the passenger on their own belongings/stuff, process time and privacy. Passengers feel freedom of choices, will feel responsible, will understand and trust the agents and can more easy predict their journey through the airport. The safety aspect is located in the obligation that passengers have to submit themselves to various checks to ensure safety, but when the passengers want, with the information they want and with the supervision on their belongings/stuff.

GUEST FRIENDLINESS <> FLOW

Offering good service contributes to the guest friendliness. Agents are the faces of the service offered in the area and thereby are of main importance. The task of an agent has to shift from being a guard to being a service assistant that pays

close attention. Personal attention, information and help will be needed to create service excellence and create satisfied passengers. However next to this personal focus the flow within the security area is important.

As Schiphol Airport will grow in the coming years, more passengers will need to go through security areas. Creating more capacity by increasing the amount of checkpoints and lanes to solve this is only a temporary solution. To solve the problem the behavior of passengers should be influenced: They cause the main delay. To influence them a personal focus has to be applied that makes them comfortable with the area: Trust, clarity, service, and a being relaxed create a comfortable feeling.

DESIGN VISION IN SHORT

The airport will offer the passengers a freedom of choice in the security area and will stimulate and challenge the passengers to take the control and responsibility over their own travel, belongings and actions. Personal attentions for individual passengers and mutual respect between passengers and agents will result in trust, collaboration, comfort and core. Individuals in the mass have the control on aspects that involve only their person, but are supervised to keep up the flow and the level of safety needed. The environment of the security is inspiring and inviting for passengers and recalls feelings of clarity, predictability, comprehension and comfort.

IDEA GENERATION

In the current section we summarize how the findings are translated into ideas for a feasible and challenging concept for future security areas.

PERSONAS

As a first step personas are created and used to give a human face to abstract user data. Here three large passenger groups can be defined. These groups require different types of services in the security area due to their different experiences, expectations, attitudes and goals. The personas are given a fictional name and characteristics that are consistent with the user group they belong to. The personas are used to create empathy with the diverse user groups and to evaluate the ideas for each user group to create an optimal fit. This section provides an overview of the three passenger

personas, the agent persona and their preferences for future security, see figure 3.

Run | Mister Lee is a successful businessman working sixty hours a week. For his work he travels monthly to establishments of his company in other countries within Europe. He can be considered as a routine traveller. Loss of time is the most important aspect for this persona in the security area. The passenger wants to go as quickly as possible through the security and is fine with self-service actions to speed up the process. When additional payments are required the passenger is willing to pay, but he expects additional speed and comfort. The persona has a lot of experience with flying, so he does not need additional information. The Run category is available for Privium, Premium and Gold members of airlines. Also passengers that have flown more than 5 times in a year can apply for a Run card. This boundary for entering Run is created to hold on to the exclusive feeling of Run and to prevent that everyone will enter Run because it is faster.

Fun | Family Metselaars is a small family existing of father Jan, mother Laura and two children: Max and Lisa, respectively 6 and 4 years old. Once a year they go on holiday with the family for two weeks, preferably to a warm country within Europe. Passengers that consider ‘fun’ the most important are in general families with small children that are quickly distracted and people who travel rarely. They are in a vacation mood and want to make an experience of their trip. Some additional help is appreciated for children that do not want to cooperate or people who travel for the first time.

Care | Thea de Wit is 65 years old, but still very active for her age. She used to work as a physiotherapist, but she retired 6 years ago. At the moment she spends her time doing voluntary work, baby sitting her grandchildren and working in the garden. A few times a year she is going on short trips to family and friends. Some of her old friends are living in Spain and Italy. Passengers that prefer care are mainly people with a reduced mobility, a lack of knowledge about digital machines and elderly. Service and helpful employees within the filter are important for them. They have the time and do not want to feel rushed.

The analysis phase showed the importance of one specific group of people in the security that can make or break the security experience: The security agents. They are the face of the security area, the service assistant, the guards guaranteeing safety and they control the process flow. Therefore the persona security agent is discussed here as well to be able to see and judge the different security concepts from his/her point of view and to create empathy with this ‘user’ group.

Figure 3. Persona's

Agent Ben is 29 years old and working as a security agent. Due to his preference for working with security and ranks, he applied for a job as a security agent. After a few years of working as a security agent he is thinking about quitting. The working conditions are very hard, he often doesn't feel respected and he is exhausted after a day of work. Some things really need to change to make him stay.

Creating a pleasant working environment for the security agents is another driving factor of this graduation project. This topic has become important due to increasing problems of finding enough suitable security agents (Schiphol Group, 2010). A new role for the security agents is wishful. The interviews with agents in the analysis phase showed that agents currently feel under pressure during their work (Hoogervorst, 2010). The agents have a lot of responsibilities for a job that is seen as quite low level. They are responsible for the flow, a thorough safety check, assisting passengers, providing information, welcoming passengers and radiating charisma. The agent furthermore feels time pressure of the key performance indicators and the mystery guest checks. All together the agent has a lot of tasks and responsibilities to focus on, in an environment that makes it even worse: It is dark, noisy and musty.

In the future concept security agents get a different role: The design vision prescribed that the amount of responsibilities of the agent need to be reduced to relieve the pressure. Currently all tasks of the agents are focused on safety. In the new concept the tasks of the agent will change to surveillance, observation and offering service. Hereby the agent has time to focus on guest friendliness, next to assuring safety. Together with the defined feelings of the agent in the future security a change in attitude can be realized by performing a ‘role abstraction’. An abstraction hierarchy of the current tasks of the security agents can bring back the core of the work of the security agent (Stappers, van der Lugt, Hekkert & Sleswijk Visser, 2007).

BRAINSTORMING

The first ideas were generated through two brainstorm sessions with both internal and external people, in order to gain more ideas, inspiration and information. The external session was the first session that was executed. With seven participants and one facilitator a 2.5-hour session was done. The starting topics existed of ‘how to’ questions created around the parameters of the design vision: Guest friendliness, flow, safety and personal control. With these parameters as basis, ideas were created and all input was converged into practical ideas that fit the current design goal. The focus of the internal session was to create support within the organization for the graduation topic and to gather thoughts and ideas living among the Airport employees, likely from a more realistic point of view. This input was also used to verify the ideas that were developed before. The internal participants were selected from different departments of the Schiphol Group, to ensure input from different perspectives. The internal session existed of six participants of Schiphol and a facilitator and lasted also 2.5 hours. A lot of ideas were generated with the outcomes of the analysis study, the results of the brainstorm sessions and knowledge on users, process and technology described in part four. In total more than 300 different ideas were created in all kinds of directions. The ideas mainly provided solutions for small aspects in the future security area. To create a structure in all generated ideas, ideas were clustered. Figure 4 illustrates this process.

Figure 4. Process, idea generation till concept

Cluster-groups were created based on topics of the design vision. The degree to which the idea was linked to one of these topics determined in which cluster -group the idea was located. For each cluster-group similarities between ideas were found that created sub-clusters, as can be seen in the table below. In total 30 cluster-groups were created.

SELECTION

As all ideas captured small solutions for parts of the security area, an additional step had to be made before going to concepts. Combinations of ideas had to be made to create diverse total security settings that could be compared with each other. This combination of ideas that together creates an idea for the future security concept, is called an idea cluster. One inspiring idea out of one of the cluster-groups was chosen based on originality, fit with the design vision and degree of provocation. This idea became the ‘mother idea’ for that moment. From the other cluster-groups interesting ideas were searched that could enrich this mother idea. When,

with this method, an idea was created that covered the whole security area, this idea became one idea cluster. This process was repeated with different ‘mother ideas’ till the most promising ideas of the cluster-groups were used and enough diverse idea clusters were generated. In total thirteen idea clusters were created and six sub-solutions that are interesting to integrate in the idea clusters in a later stadium, see figure 5 for the idea selection. The used judging elements are explained in the next paragraph.

	SECURITY PARK	1- SECURITY	TRAVELPLAN	LEAPEROG	FAMILY SCAN	THEATERPROF & AT THE BAKERY	FOLLOW THE LINE	AVVD REURMERK	UPI 1	UPI 2	AT RANDOM	GREEN SEC
* feel important	3	4	4	3	2	4	4	2	1	2	1	3
* personal coach	4	5	5	2	3	3	4	3	1	2	2	4
* mutual empathy	4	3	3	3	3	4	5	1	1	3	2	1
* phase transitions	3	3	0	3	2	4	4	2	3	4	4	2
* evoke curiosity	5	5	3	4	3	3	4	1	2	3	3	4
	19	20	15*	15	13	18	21	9	8	14	12	14

Figure 5: Idea selection

PRODUCT: SECURITY CONVERSATION

This section discusses the creation of the product, in other words ‘the future security concept’. It starts with the underlying framework and continues with a description of the product and its characteristics for the future security area. The explanation of the product is based on a metaphor: A good conversation. This metaphor illustrates the similarities with phases of the framework. Based on this part it can be concluded that when the security area integrates the thoughts behind ‘a good conversation’ in the future security, the basis for a security area with a human perspective is created. The product is therefore called ‘Security Conversation’. This section ends with interaction elements that represent the intended interactions in the future security area.

FRAMEWORK

As a result of a study on the similarities between the diverse idea clusters a common ground could be extracted. All ideas clusters were built upon six key aspects, which form the basis for the translation of the design vision into a future security concept. These key aspects were compared to the list of

requirements to ensure that the created framework meets the expectations that were created at the end of the analysis phase and the framework results in a ‘human focus’ of the security area. Below the six key aspects are explained shortly, stressing why it is important to be part of the framework of the final design.

Key aspect 1. Space arrangement

The analysis phase shows that there is too much distraction in the current security area due to the fact that all steps are located in one space: the information, the queues, the scanning materials and the reclaim. To create more calmness and control in the security area and above all more clarity, different phases will be created. Furthermore, passengers want to feel as a guest. Feeling welcome at the entrance, knowing one can ask for help and hearing thank you at the end will create a positive feeling among passengers. Integrating the waiting area in the security area will reduce the discomfort of waiting. The design vision is represented by this framework element as it results in more control and guest friendliness and above all it strengthens the look & feel by improving the clarity and comfort of the area.

The following division was found in all idea clusters:

- 1) A clear entrance, a security process separated from the rest of the airport, orientation possibilities, a personal welcome and a calm down area.
- 2) Information on the security process is offered and passengers can prepare themselves in a comfortable way (sit while waiting) for the security phase (This phase can go together with phase 1).
- 3) Scanning area in which the passenger experiences personal control and the security agents have the supervision. A high degree of self-service.
- 4) Clear exit of the scanning area. Place to dress up if needed, to orientate and to calm down. When leaving the security area a personal ‘thanks and have a good trip’ is exposed.

The first and last elements are essential for two reasons. First to let passengers focus on the security process without being distracted and, because they are informed, their speed will increase. Second to transform the negative expectation currently

experienced by passengers, into a positive expectation by means of the pleasant personal goodbye when leaving the area.

Key aspect 2. Look & feel typography

Clarity of information was an important outcome of the passenger research and is represented in the look & feel of the design vision. Information has to be offered in a clear, simple and short way. As the postings at airside are large and visible from a distance to orientate yourself, the indications in the security area have to be too. The retail store Albert Heijn uses in his XL stores a very clear and distinctive way of indicating which product can be found where. With big letters and short, almost childish terms, different areas are indicated. When the area around is spatial and clear, these indications can also be used to orientate yourself and to see which steps are coming.

Key aspect 3. Differentiate

The context analysis showed the increasing popularity of passenger differentiation. By offering passengers a service adjusted to their needs, personal control and guest friendliness are guaranteed. An interesting side effect is that passengers that require more service do not delay frequent travelers. The groups that will be used for differentiation are the described persona groups. In short, the implications for the security area as a result of the differentiation based on the three personas are as following. For Run: Quick process, no additional features, no distractions and excellent service. For Fun: Mainly for families to distract kids and for passengers traveling for the first time. The actions are the same at the Run category, but an experience is added. For Care additional service are offered, mainly for the self-service elements in the security area.

Key aspect 4. Task division

The design vision showed the image of a person standing on stilts and balancing between guest friendliness and flow, while having personal control and safety as foundation. In that situation the responsibilities of the agent were safety, flow and guest friendliness. In the new security concept the responsibilities for the tasks are changed. The agent

is responsible for the safety by mainly observation and profiling, and is responsible for the guest friendliness. This combination releases the weight on the shoulders of the agent and causes that safety and guest friendliness are better secured.

The passenger gets the responsibility for the flow. The surrounding will support the passenger in taking the responsibility, by for example offering differentiation, giving rewards when stimulating the flow, by offering the passenger overview and control. Passengers have the control over the self-service aspects, but the agents have the supervision. When a passenger is acting strange or not operating the machines in the right way, an agent will keep an eye on him or her.

Key aspect 5. Flexibility

The security technologies available in 2020 are under development at the moment. However, it is hard to say when these techniques reach maturity to guarantee an almost 100% safety. Therefore the techniques used in the future security concept function as an indication for what might work at that moment. The chosen technique must be applied in such a way that it is be replaceable for other security screening options, when the technique turns out to be not mature enough to apply. As safety is one of the parameters of the design vision the future security concept must guarantee almost 100% safety without reducing the personal control.

Key aspect 6. Public vs personal

The analysis showed that all handlings in the security area, private or not, take place in the public area. Passengers feel embarrassed when they need to do things they preferable would do in a private space, e.g. walking on your socks. As the future security area must radiate guest friendliness, it must offer passengers public and personal areas. Of the four described security areas, the third area (the scanning area) offers a private place mainly during scanning time. In the two calm down areas passengers can choose for a more public or more private waiting area, which is determined by the space around them. The design principles of Schiphol process RPP (redesign passenger process) support this element as they include public versus private

and space versus individual in their design implications.

FUTURE SECURITY CONCEPT

This section discusses how the framework has led to the final product for the new security area. This section emphasizes the integration of the human perspective in the future security area. It includes the role of people in this framework, resulting in a description of the various interactions that take place in the security area. To see a clear difference between the current and the new situation, first the current situation is shortly described. Concrete interaction elements are defined that represents the interactions that are part of the product. These elements are used to determine whether an idea cluster fits the product.

CURRENT SITUATION

To stress the difference between the current security process and the process of the future security concept, the current situation is described briefly below. "After the check in a passenger follows the signs on the boarding towards the security filter. When arriving the passenger needs to join the queue. In the distance the passenger sees a board with security on it, so he knows it is the queue to the security that he is joining. How much time it is going to take is hard to say. Let's call the area the passenger is standing in the 'queuing area'. At the end of the queuing area the boarding with security information shows up for a moment as well as a glimpse of the process the passenger has to go through. The security agent at the entrance of the area asks for the ticket of the passenger. After this action the passenger enters the security area. First standing in the queue again while hearing the agents shout what passengers can and cannot take along. When the passenger is screened and has collected his hand luggage, the passenger enters the dress-up area. A few ad-hoc tables are located here, but still quite far away to reach on your socks. It is quite unclear where the security area ends and the passenger is looking around to find information to continue his trip on the airport. As he can not find the information he is looking for, he walks into the familiar shopping hall." Concluding, the following phases can be defined in the security area:

- The queuing area. Long queues standing before the security area, without a clue where to stand and what will happen next.
- Scanning area in which passengers hand over the control to the security agents. Passengers do what they are told to and leave the process as quickly as possible.
- The scanning area flows into the dress up 'area' in which some tables are placed. Where the security stops is unclear. General flight information can be found when paying close attention at the end of the security on big postings.

Next these phases are compared to the phases of the framework described in the previous section. The future situation is explained using the metaphor a good conversation. This metaphor was chosen based on the structure of a business conversation, which has clear similarities with the phases described in the framework. Furthermore the rituals before entering and ending the conversation have an overlap with the actions that needs to be performed in the security area. To deepen the knowledge on the structure of a business conversation before translating this to the future security, the phases will be studied briefly. These five phases can be distinguished in a business conversation as well, see figure 6.

Figure 6: Steps in a conversation

1. *Before the conversation:* Awareness on the content of the conversation and the conversation partner. Consider what to discuss and your point of view.
2. *The preparatory phase:* Greet, welcome and social talk. The goal is to determine the atmosphere of the conversation. Welcome rituals such as offer a chair, coffee are common examples.
3. *The core phase.* Purpose of conversation, negotiate and reach agreement. Goals are to discuss

reason, structure, preconditions and planning phase), reach meeting goal and consensus, sum up agreements and make new appointments (closure phase).

4. The round off phase with social talk, 'doorstep remarks', goodbye. Main goal is to exchange final thoughts and start leaving 'ritual'.
5. After the conversation. People leave the area and reconsider all that has been discussed and agreed upon in the business meeting.

There are various implications for security for each phase. Before entering the security, passengers need to be aware of what they can expect. They have to get the opportunity to read some information in advance. When the passenger enters the area, a security agent welcomes the passenger, offers help when needed and reassures the passenger. This results in a friendly atmosphere in the security area. The passenger feels welcome due to the comfortable furniture and the personal information offered in the area. The hierarchical relation is transferred into mutual respect. At the entrance of the scanning phase, the most important conditions and information is offered briefly to the passenger again. At the end of the scanning area the agent can ask the passenger to join him to the re-scan cabins. After the scanning phase passengers enter the round off area and can wait for relatives, dress up and calm down. In/at the end of the area an agent will say goodbye. The passenger can be given 'a thought for the road'.

The conversation metaphor is used as a basis for the security design. The metaphor 'a good conversation' explains why the personal approach that is present in a good conversation is essential in the security area as well. Derived from this metaphor six elements are defined that are crucial in a passenger friendly security area:

Guest friendly entrance and exit. An element that the security area can borrow from 'a good conversation' is a clear entrance and exit. In a conversation an entrance is always followed by a welcome and an exit by a goodbye. When the passenger enters the area a security agent welcomes the passenger, offers help when needed and

reassures the passenger. This results in a guest friendly atmosphere in the security area.

Transitions. The metaphor mentioned five transitions in 'a good conversation'. These transitions can be applied to the security area to offer passenger clarity and control on what happens next.

Start-up and round-off. The good thing about a conversation is the preparation and closure time you have as a visitor. A relaxed atmosphere, in which you are already in the room of the conversation, but you have time to orientate yourself and to prepare. You calm down by removing your coat, orientating and chitchatting. After the scanning phase the passenger enters the round off area and can wait for relatives, dress up and calm down. At the end of the area an agent will say goodbye and wishes a pleasant trip.

Personal comfort. Passengers feel welcome by the personal greetings of the agent, the comfortable furniture and the personal information offered.

Scan and guide

The next thing that can be learned is the transition from calming down, towards starting to prepare each other on the content of the appointment, by asking for contextual information. In the security area this phase can be used to hand out information on the security to the passenger: At the entrance of the scanning phase the most important conditions and information are offered briefly again. In the conversation the partners guide each other through the things that need to be discussed. This feeling of working together and offering a helping hand need to be represented in the scanning area as well: A personal guide will be offered.

Manage expectations

Before entering the security area passengers need to be aware of what they can expect. They have to get the opportunity to read some information in advance. When leaving the security area the passenger can be given 'a thought for the road'.

Mutual respect

The core of the appointment is the security-screening phase. In a conversation people exchange

thoughts and listen to each other. An interaction is taking place there. In the security area this interaction shows up as a friendly communication between passenger and (service) agent. The passenger has the control and the agent has the supervision. They need to work together. The hierarchical relation is transferred to mutual respect. As a conversation is face to face to observe each other's expressions, an agent can tell the emotions on someone's face for profiling purposes. Currently the agents do not have the time to profile.

INTERACTION ELEMENTS

Now the characteristics of the product for the future security are described. We discuss how these characteristics are taken along in this report. In the next chapters one of the idea clusters will be chosen as representation of the product. This idea cluster has been developed into an 'Implementation Concept', which function as an example of how the product can be realized in 2020. To find out which of the idea clusters fits the product the most, interaction elements are created. These describe which interactions the chosen Implementation Concept should facilitate. The interaction elements were created by combining the characteristics of the product with the overall design vision and distracting the core interactions that need to take place in the future security area. The interaction elements will function as support for the product in the rest of the design process: The final design should support the product in all aspects.

Interaction elements: product-person

Feel important

The passenger has to feel as a guest in the area. Information is offered in a comprehensible, personal and approachable way. The purpose is to offer the feeling of having a choice and being in control to create confident and collaborative passengers. An exclusive treatment can be chosen.

Personal coach

The human-product self-service items in the security area will offer personal guidance when the passenger wishes and helps to reassure passengers. At the same time they stimulate the passenger to take the responsibility, discover things themselves and keep up with the flow.

Mutual empathy

The security stimulates empathy between agent and passenger. In this way a collaborative interaction will take place in which passengers respect the supervision tasks of the agent and the agent can rely on the passenger and predict his/her behavior.

Interaction elements: environment

Phase transitions

The interaction changes in each phase and thereby the role of passenger and security agent as well. Furthermore the security has a clear start and ending point. At both sides human interaction takes place to feel appreciated.

Evoke curiosity

When people have to wait for their turn and can only see a glimpse of the next phase, they will get curious. The security zone distract passenger from the security process by showing projections on the walls.

CONCEPT SELECTION

The design process resulted in thirteen idea clusters and six sub-solutions. This selection has been based on the interaction elements and feasibility factors derived from the analysis phase. Schiphol uses the following main criteria when judging ideas:

- 1) Is it human?
- 2) Is it attainable?
- 3) Is it affordable?

These three criteria are used to group all judging criteria to result in a familiar structure for Schiphol. The first selection, the fit with the product, was discussed by the first criteria, 'Is it human?'. The second and third criteria were addressed in the second selection, the feasibility study. The weighted objectives method (Rozenburg & Eekels, 2001) was chosen to indicate which criteria are more important than others. Next to the previously discussed criteria, all concepts finally should meet all demands that are listed in the list of requirements for the new security area (Hoogervorst, 2010). This results in one idea cluster that has been elaborated into one concept. Elements from the other idea clusters are used as add-ons.

Concerning the five criteria that were mentioned the capacity is the most important one, followed by the required space and amount of agents. This high importance is caused by the need to expand the filter to be able to handle more passengers in a more pleasant way in the future.

Criteria	factor	1 - Security	Follow the line	Security park	At the lobby & theaterproof
Feasibility technology	2	(3) 6	(2) 4	(1) 2	(4) 8
Capacity	4	(2) 8	(4) 16	(1) 4	(3) 12
Amount of agents	3	(1) 3	(4) 12	(2) 6	(3) 9
Required space	3	(2) 6	(4) 12	(1) 3	(3) 9
Financial contribution	1	(1) 1	(4) 4	(2) 2	(3) 3
Wow-factor	1	(2) 2	(3) 3	(4) 4	(1) 1
		26	51	21	42

Figure 8. Concept ranking

The feasibility of the technology has an average importance and financial contribution the least, as it is more a pleasant additional circumstance. The wow-factor is added as sixth element as the final concept represents the design vision for 2020. It must be inspiring, attractive and convincing. The idea clusters were ranked with regard to each other, see figure 8. For each criteria points had to be divided, four point for the best idea cluster, one point for the least.

VISUALIZATIONS

To enhance and present the Implementation Concept the total design of the new security area is captured in 3D images. The visualizations are representations of all elements discussed in part eight ‘detailing concept’, see figure 9. The different zones are indicated. When comparing this image with the product, the phases prescribed in the product are represented by the concept. The ‘conversation’ is translated into the different zones and the interactions that are taking place. In this concept the three personas are the core. As all three personas require different levels of service, the security is divided in three areas, with three different entrances: Run, Fun and Care.

Figure 9. Future security concept

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

With the service concept “Security Conversation” and the example of the Implementation Concept a new security is created that is designed around the passenger. The main conclusion of this report is thereby that the development of a security with a human perspective, as the title of this report implies, is possible. Security can treat passengers as a guest without needing to reduce the safety level of the area or the flow of the process. The main conclusions will be discussed from the perspective of the passengers and the airport.

PASSENGERS

The look & feel of the security area and new interactions defined within, improve the passenger experience by enhancing the feeling of safety and charisma in the scanning area, adding a guest friendly feeling in the calm down and orientation area and improving the overall process flow. Passengers will enter security with are positive expectation instead of a negative one. As the technology is new, passengers need to get the time to get comfortable with the new way of going through security. Therefore, they are guided through the process by service assistants, clear information as well as by guiding technologies.

The Implementation Concept facilitates a distinguished Premium passenger process, referred to as Run and a passengers with reduced mobility process, referred to as Care. The third category is Fun, which is more focused at families with children that go for the airport experience as they consider the trip a part of their vacation.

AMSTERDAM AIRPORT

The quality perception of the airport was dominated by security as one of the main points of dissatisfaction. With the introduction of the 'Security Conversation' the quality perception of Schiphol in general will rise and thereby the airport will come a step closer to her ambition to be the preferred airport in Europe. Schiphol will be an example for other airports when introducing the 'Security Conversation' due to its innovative nature and the passenger focus. It offers the airport the opportunity to compete, by excellent service and quality, with the price fighters. Additionally the concept allows for a flexible capacity offering between the three categories Run, Fun and Care that can be adjusted to the capacity request of the moment. The technology enables a more secure security check as it combines behavioral data, remote body feature and object detection. Furthermore the technology enables an increased process flow as more passengers can be scanned at the same time and no preparation is needed.

SECURITY AGENTS

In the 'Security Conversation' the pressure at the shoulders of the security agents is relieved. The agents will become motivated workers with more variation and responsibility in their job. The atmosphere in the concept offers them a pleasant working environment. This will result in fewer turnovers among the staff of the security companies and thereby it will be easier to maintain qualified agents. All together the aspects described result in a realization of the design goal. The Implementation Concept gives security a reliable, unified and strong appearance. The ad hoc feeling that the current security recalls is not present in the Implementation Concept. Within Schiphol Group, the Security Conversation functions as an eye opener. The belief that security 'is the way it is' can be broken and

support within the organization can be created with help of this new concept. The proposed concept seems to enable the paradigm shift and interestingly, discussions have been started on implementing the Security Conversation in the future airport security plans.

ORGANIZATION

The effects of this focus shift on security issues in organizational terms became clear one year after this research. The security department of the airport added a new value to their innovation values: Passenger experience. One of the employees was made responsible for the passenger experience in all security optimizations or new security areas. Currently a large investment is pending in which a change in security set-up for 2020 is the core. As experience has become an important value, one of the project teams that are working on this new security area, is focused on ambiance and passenger experience to make sure it is not added after the realization of the security area, but already taken into account in the concept creation phase. In the security area itself a shift can be noticed from agents that have all control, to passengers that are partly in control as well and have a choice in certain process steps. Differentiation in passenger groups is one of these elements and preparing your luggage by yourself as well. These are the first steps to a passenger focused security area, but the new security area in 2020 will be a possibility to apply all given advices in this paper in practice.

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